

Numbers

**Difficulty
understanding
numbers and
carrying out
basic calculations**

Existing tools

**Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...**

What would help?

**Simpler
processes?**

Help?

Easy to use app?

Numbers

**Difficulty
transposing
numbers
correctly**

Existing tools

**Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...**

What would help?

**Simpler
processes?**

Help?

Easy to use app?

Numbers

Difficulty making
calls due to not
understanding
numbers

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Simpler
processes?

Help?

Easy to use app?

Numbers

Difficulty using
money due to
not
understanding
the value of
money

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Simpler
processes?

Help?

Easy to use app?

Numbers

Difficulty using
bank cards due
to not
understanding
the value of
money

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Simpler
processes?

Help?

Easy to use app?

